

Singularis: Reforming the Communication of Scientific Knowledge

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Abstract

- We argue that the key bottleneck in science is the research paper as a medium for communicating and storing knowledge. This inefficient format shapes the incentive structure in academia and is the major cause of the reproducibility, serials, and peer review crises.
- Reforming the publishing system is difficult because most academic performance metrics revolve around publishing data as academic papers. Changes must be evolutionary and seamless.
- We propose that communicating data as nanopublications connected within an argumentation graph can be a more efficient way to communicate knowledge to both humans and AI algorithms. This format can create an entirely new and efficient type of interaction with knowledge, also helping to resolve the pressing crises.
- A successful reform of scientific communication requires migration of substantial amounts of data from research papers into a new format. Current AI technologies enable converting large volumes of documents, making the transition to a new publishing practice feasible.

Platform under development

<https://singularis.ac/>

Key hypotheses justifying project feasibility

- Determine whether the argumentation graph format can reinforce strategic reading.
- Determine whether a standard argumentation graph format can annotate most research articles despite different writing styles.
- Determine whether AI algorithms can accurately annotate research papers with argumentation graphs.

Why are research papers inefficient as a format for data communication, and why are they the key bottleneck for science?

Scientific papers are inefficient in communicating knowledge to humans and machines. Scientific articles, invented centuries ago, no longer match how knowledge is produced, shared, and evaluated today. But do research papers still serve their original purpose: communicating research knowledge efficiently? Studies show that students and scientists rarely read papers linearly. Instead, they skip, skim, and use complex strategies to extract the information they need [1], a practice called “strategic reading.” Thus, articles are suboptimal for communicating knowledge to human researchers.

FACT #1

Modern papers are difficult for computer algorithms to read. Even simple search tasks, such as finding all published experiments in which a specific cell type was treated with a particular chemical compound, used to require hours of manual work in the pre-AI era. Today, data annotation and database building still require human curation, and fully automated extraction has not yet been achieved.

FACT #2

Citations are insufficient for navigation. They connect fragments of knowledge across papers, but provide little context for these connections. To understand a citation, a reader must locate it in the citing paper and sometimes read the cited paper to find the exact experiment or claim.

FACT #3

ANALYSIS #1 *Therefore, narrative papers remain inefficient for both human scientists and AI systems, and more structured formats are needed.*

CONCLUSION #1

Peer review crisis. Evaluating research papers is increasingly time-consuming. Area experts must assess lengthy, specialized manuscripts, while the growing number of studies places increasing demands on peer review. At the same time, reviewers are often said to be the only people who read a paper from beginning to end. Peer review is thus increasingly disconnected from strategic reading practices. These imbalances contribute to journals’ difficulties in finding reviewers, a problem often described as a “peer review crisis” [2].

ANALYSIS #2

FACT #4

Citation-based metrics are inaccurate. A more complex issue is the evaluation of scientific merit. How original, important, and impactful are the results? These judgments shape careers, projects, and funding. In practice, quality is judged by the impact factor of the journal where it appears.

Why rely on journal reputation rather than article citation counts? Citation counts are highly imperfect measures of quality and impact. Method papers are often cited far more than many other kinds of work: for example, the method for protein electrophoresis [3] is cited about 26 times more than Watson and Crick’s foundational paper on DNA structure [4, 5]. Review articles are highly cited while siphoning citations from the original studies they summarize [6]. Irreproducible findings have been cited more frequently than reproducible ones [7]. Citation practices are further biased by prestige [8], positively framed titles [9], self-citations [10], and other factors [11]. Citation-based evaluation also disadvantages recently published work, which has not yet had time to accumulate citations.

FACT #5

ANALYSIS #3 *As a result, the evaluation system relies largely on journal reputation. But journal-impact-factor-based assessment is not necessarily fair or balanced. Publication in prestigious journals is a highly politicized and poorly predictable process involving a small number of reviewers and editors. While expert judgment is valuable, the final publication decision is often made before the paper’s content is exposed to wider critical scrutiny. The evaluation is therefore incomplete.*

FACT #6

ANALYSIS #4 *These incentives also create structural problems. In the race to “publish high,” scientists may ignore valuable data that cannot be easily presented as a high-impact finding. They may also spend years assembling one large paper, while intermediate results remain hidden.*

FACT #7 **Serials crisis.** The privileged gatekeeping position of academic journals allows them to raise publication fees, creating inequalities between scientists with different levels of funding. Paywalled access also restricts the dissemination of knowledge often produced with public funding, further slowing scientific progress.

FACT #8 **The reproducibility crisis.** Stress and uncertainty create incentives for misconduct, including exaggeration of effect sizes, overselling conclusions, or even fabrication. This contributes to a large number of irreproducible reports, even in areas such as cancer research [12]. Publishing replication studies is poorly incentivized. Journals tend to value novel findings that are more likely to be cited than replication papers that may strengthen the original findings, but may not be well cited themselves.

ANALYSIS #5 Publishing negative replication outcomes may be even harder, since reviewers may demand repeated experiments with the original reagents and apply greater scrutiny. Thus, the reproducibility crisis stems in part from the incentive structure, which is shaped by how data are communicated and evaluated.

FACT #9 **Minor results often go unpublished.** The existing system disincentivize publishing technology calibrations, orphan findings, serendipitous observations, and other small pieces of reliable data, as they will be largely invisible and will bring citation scores. Publishing such information in a searchable format could change the incentives and substantially accelerate scientific progress.

ANALYSIS #6

CONCLUSION #2 *Thus, at major crises of contemporary academia, peer review, reproducibility, serial, and unpublished fraction of data are rooted in the research article as the main medium for communicating knowledge, and the incentives determined by this format.*

CONCLUSION #3 **Why does the system not change?** If a new model of scientific communication were introduced, the first researchers to adopt it would risk losing their position under the current rules. Their formal metrics would decline, along with their career prospects and funding opportunities. Since key indicators are tied to papers, a sudden transition is unrealistic.

HYPOTHESIS #1 *That is why a new system of scientific communication must, at least initially, coexist with the current publication system rather than try to replace it outright.*

Singularis: radical transformation through gradual evolution

TECHNIQUE #1 **The approach.** Our main innovation is to reduce the minimum unit of publishable scientific data. An independently published element could be a single hypothesis, experiment, result, dataset, conclusion, or method. Elements are connected through typed, informative links that organize logical flow. Known facts can point to hypotheses, hypotheses to experiments, experiments to results, results to conclusions, and reproductions or refutations to the claims they address.

HYPOTHESIS #2 *Singularis, therefore, represents knowledge as an argumentation graph, where logical elements are nodes and relations between them are edges [13].*

Why are such nanopublications difficult within the current system? Concise publications would be lost in the vast literature without being clearly attached to relevant domains. Citations are not typed, and relationships between different logical operations are not formalized. Researchers would struggle to find such small data pieces, understand their value, and connect them within broader knowledge.

ANALYSIS #7 **Seamless transition.** The key idea of Singularis is coexistence with the traditional system. Singularis elements can be published before, alongside, or after conventional papers. Data published as elements can still appear in traditional articles, and vice versa. Singularis can therefore function as a preprint server, a

Figure 1. A. Singularis plan to mitigate crises in science. Starting by supplementing research papers with argumentation graphs to support strategic reading, we plan to implement new protocols for how data is communicated, stored, and assessed. In the future, this reform should contribute to resolving multiple shortcomings in science that are rooted in the inefficiency of research papers as a format for data communication. **B.** Singularis argumentation graph constructed for this essay. The exact rules governing graph construction are under active development and may change.

peer-reviewed journal, or a post-publication annotation platform and database. Initially, it would complement the existing system; in the long run, it could replace it.

EXPERIMENT #1 **Reinforcing strategic reading and navigation.** Our first step is to develop the Singularis format to communicate data more effectively to both humans and machines. Currently, Singularis supplements a traditional PDF with an argumentation graph that captures the study's logical structure, reinforcing strategic reading (Fig 1). By selecting specific elements, the reader is directed to the relevant place in the manuscript. Our preliminary assessment suggests that such graphs can improve the speed and efficiency of strategic reading. In the next stages, we will integrate graphs from multiple papers into larger structures that reflect the development of entire fields. This will create a completely new way of interaction with knowledge.

HYPOTHESIS #4 **Research quality assessment and solving the peer review crisis.** We hypothesize that representing data as an argumentation graph will make peer review and author responses more efficient. The graph can help structure criticisms from different reviewers and organize the authors' responses. We will allow researchers to comment publicly on individual elements. These comments may be anonymous, signed, or semi-anonymous (e.g., showing expertise but not identity). Comments could then be discussed and assessed: supported or criticized by other community members. This assessment will determine the quality of peer review to fairly credit the reviewers and lay the foundation for a continuous quality assessment of research.

HYPOTHESIS #5 **Impact metrics and incentives to contribute to data assessment.** Connecting thousands of papers into an argumentation graph may create a new way to evaluate scientific impact. Unlike traditional citations, links between Singularis elements carry logical meaning and can provide contextual evaluation of each contribution. Individuals' scores based on graph topology may therefore offer more accurate metrics for funding, hiring, and promotion. Their use by funding bodies could motivate scientists to improve the accuracy of the AI-generated Singularis annotations. Proposed edits would be visible to the community and accepted based on consensus or vote.

HYPOTHESIS #6 **Mitigating the reproducibility crisis.** Singularis can also change incentives for publishing replication data. A replicated experiment could be explicitly linked to the original, making it easy to find and evaluate. Replicated results could also contribute to their authors' scores when the original result is cited. By adjusting graph topology and the metrics derived from it, the research community could create incentives to publish reliable data, whether original or reproduced.

HYPOTHESIS #7 **Addressing serials crises.** Singularis is designed to advance science with lower organizational workload and lower publication costs than traditional publishing. It supports open publishing, transparent review, and community-based assessment of data quality and impact, which may help mitigate the gatekeeping.

HYPOTHESIS #8 **Changing the incentives from competition to collaboration.** A large amount of data – such as negative results, orphan findings, raw data – is currently not considered worth publishing. Singularis can change this by allowing granular data pieces to be published in a searchable, visible, annotated, and credit-bearing format. Scientists may be incentivized to publish results as soon as they are produced, rather than waiting until a full “big paper” is complete. This would allow them to establish credit early, while enabling others to use the results immediately. Raw dataset published on Singularis, if later analyzed by another group, could be credited to the original authors, comparable to co-authorship on a follow-up paper. This could greatly increase incentives to publish raw data and intermediate results. The resulting increase in the speed of collective progress may justify wider sharing of credit across a global collaborative network, shaping the spirit of the scientific community.

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